

D4.3: Regional Training Workshops

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Executive Summary

The main objective of the LoCloud project is to ease the task of small and medium-sized heritage organisations across Europe in making their contents accessible to Europeana. An important part of LoCloud efforts is to facilitate the process of taking local data from heterogeneous data sources and transform it into Europeana compliant data. This process involves understanding and interpreting metadata profiles, extracting data, setting harvesting infrastructure, managing vocabularies, enriching/completing data, mapping metadata profiles and more.

LoCloud has several work packages devoted to the development of software tools and microservices that will simplify the content contribution and ingestion process from the perspective of both content providers and Europeana. Throughout the first part of the project, time and resources has been dedicated to the development, improvement and testing prototypes of these tools. The regional training workshops, executed as part of Work Package 4, were intended to enable LoCloud content providing partners to utilize the technology implemented through Work Packages 2 and 3 – and to prepare them to deliver training in turn to their partners.

The training has two objectives whereof the first is to make all partners aware of the technologies that are available to them; the second objective is to provide an introduction to each of the tools that is thorough enough that the individual partners can start using the software and supporting their local and regional institutions.

Not all LoCloud tools are intended for all types of content providers. Some of the tools are expert systems that typically will be operated by aggregators and similar; others targeted at end-users without extensive technology skills.

Three workshops were held in Bordeaux, Poznań and Graz during the autumn of 2014. The topics covered during the workshops included: the MORE repository, the MINT ingestion tool, the LoCloud Collections (formerly Lightweight Digital Library service), the Historical Place Names service, the Vocabulary service, the Geolocation Enrichment Tools and the Enrichment Service. Finally, an introduction to the LoCloud support mechanism was provided covering the support portal, the help-desk and the questions-and-answers sub-systems.

This report provides overview of the agenda of training workshops, and summarizes their outcomes including some general recommendations for the project regarding the challenges seen as the most important by workshops participants.

1 Overview

This report documents the execution of regional training workshops arranged by AVINET and PSNC to train technical staff of participating organisations in the implementation and use of LoCloud tools and services (task 4.1.1). The training provided during one of these workshops was video-recorded to enable an edited online video to be produced to capture the main elements of this training and to make it available for repeated use (task 4.1.2).

In order to provide the best possible training, the training is being spread over two time-periods. The first round of three training workshops was between September and December 2014. A further training workshop will be held towards the end of the project, allowing for repetition, refreshing partners on the latest developments within LoCloud services and applications.

The programme of the training workshops was coordinated by PSNC with input from the technical partners as well as the project management. Locations for training workshops were determined based on (1) partners volunteering as hosts and (2) geographical distribution in order to minimize travel time and costs.

Figure 1: Geographic distribution of LoCloud Workshops

The first workshop was hosted by LoCloud partner Archives Departementales de Gironde in Bordeaux, France on 23/24 October and had 17 participants. The second workshop was held at PSNCs facilities in Poznań, Poland on 20/21 November, and had 18 participants. LoCloud partner PSNC has its own professional TV-production team¹ and the presentation-part of the trainings were recorded during the workshop in Poznań. The final workshop was hosted by AIT in Graz, Austria on 11/12 December and had 22 participants.

Figure 2: Photo of LoCloud training workshop in Poznań (21.11.2014)

The purpose of the training workshops was to make sure that LoCloud content providers are capable of utilizing LoCloud technology and supporting their local partners in its use to facilitate the process of contributing their content to Europeana. LoCloud content providers can also use training materials (slides, scenarios) to organize similar trainings for local level, if they will find that such activity is good complementation to the support provided via LoCloud Support Centre available on-line at <http://support.locloud.eu/>.

Throughout the first half of the LoCloud project, many applications and services were developed or improved. Each technical partner involved test users and test regimes during the development of their application or service, yet each content partners did not have knowledge of all of the tools. The training workshops aimed to bring all partners to a level of knowledge where they were fully aware of, and able to start using, the various tools and services offered by the project.

Section 2 of this report contains overview of the training topics. Section 3 describes the video recording process. Section 4 contains summary of the most important recommendations coming from these workshops. The training workshop programmes and attendance sheets for the events are attached in Appendices I and II respectively. Official event website is available at <http://www.locloud.eu/Events/LoCloud-Training-Workshops>.

¹ <http://www.platon.pionier.net.pl/online/telewizja.php?lang=en>

2 Training Topics

This section provides a brief description of each of the topics covered during the training workshops including a brief introduction to each topic, how the service or application fits into the Europeana content provider process and the objective of the training, i.e. what people ought to know and be able to do after completing the training.

2.1 How the training supports the overall workflow

Figure 3: The LoCloud workflow from content provider via aggregators to Europeana

The tools and services facilitate the content provision process to Europeana at many stages, starting in the local collection management systems.

The Vocabulary service permits users to import, or build, thesauri and vocabularies that are, or will be, used in local collection management systems. The historical place names service does the same, but for geographical concepts and can be used to link content to physical space – and time. Both are also possible to use as a matching source when trying to auto-enrich data that has been loaded into the LoCloud repository.

For small institutions that do not run their own dedicated infrastructure, LoCloud is offering the LoCloud Collections tool, a Software as a Service application that provides heritage institutions with a complete Cloud-hosted collection management system that is already integrated with the upstream Europeana content ingestion process into Europeana out-of-the-box.

For institutions wishing to conduct local content enrichment, i.e. upgrade the quality of data in their own databases, LoCloud offers Geolocation Enrichment Tools that permit this – the underlying services of the same geolocation enrichment tools that make it possible to add X, Y coordinates to existing heritage content. The tools also include the LoGeo geolocation API that may be invoked as part of the auto-enrichment process in the LoCloud repository.

To aid institutions in the process of mapping their local or domain-specific metadata profiles into EDM, suitable for ingestion into Europeana, LoCloud offers enhancements and further development of MINT, a highly sophisticated metadata mapping tool that has been developed through a succession of Europeana related projects.

Once transformed, the data are then loaded into the LoCloud repository built using the software MORE, a system that has had a similar history as that of MINT, conceived within and improved over a number of projects.

As part of the introduction of MORE, a demonstration was also provided on how auto-enrichment may be invoked on data that are ingested into the repository. Here, the LoCloud metadata enrichment service was demonstrated.

In addition to the individual software trainings, the workshops also included an introduction to the overall support mechanism that is intended to aid ALL steps of the content provision workflow, wherever any of the partners or their contributors face challenges.

2.2 Training concept

The workshops were targeting LoCloud content provider partners – but in many cases, LoCloud partners are aggregators or institutions that rely on data from underlying or sibling institutions and will provide support for these in how to get started with and use the LoCloud tools and services, hence “training the trainers” as is specified in the LoCloud DoW. This approach secures a wider outreach than what would have been possible if workshops were to target all “final” end-users.

Each topic that was introduced during the workshop followed the same template-approach: First, a presentation or introduction was given, providing an overview of the software application/service. The features were introduced and a step-by-step demonstration was given.

Second, attendants were invited to conduct a number of simple, guided exercises where the instructor demonstrated a typical workflow on a big projector screen while the attendants tried to do the same process on their own computers and, in some cases, with their own data.

Finally, each section was rounded off by a discussion on possible improvements and clarifications related to the software – and the training session.

2.3 LoCloud Collections (lightweight digital library prototype)

For institutions without dedicated IT-infrastructure, LoCloud has implemented a cloud-hostable collection management system that is integrated with the Europeana content ingestion workflow. In order to enable LoCloud-partners to instruct their prospective content providers on how to get started with this software, it was included in the training workshops.

This Software-as-a-Service application, available at <http://locloudhosting.net/>, is based on modified and customized version of the open source CMS Omeka. It permits small institutions to build their own interactive digital libraries “in the cloud” without the necessity for locally installed software or hardware beyond a PC and an Internet connection. LoCloud Collections provides users with the possibility of having their own Omeka installation running in the cloud in less than 5 minutes and is connected with other LoCloud services to facilitate delivery of metadata to Europeana.

The training provided an overview of the basic service functionality, from registering, to creating own digital library, configuring it and putting content on-line. The way of integration of LoCloud Collections with MORE was also presented.

Having completed the training, attendants shall be able to setup a new LoCloud Collections instance as well as create and manage content via the web based user interface.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/LoCloud%20Collections>

Deliverable: D2.5. Lightweight Digital Library Prototype (LoCloud Collections Service)

2.4 MORE

The last step on the way from content-provider to Europeana is the LoCloud repository through which the majority of content contributed in LoCloud will pass. MORE aggregates data from all content providers together in harmonized form. These data are available for post-processing via a range of API methods and an end-user interface that among other things enable auto-enrichment of content. It is from this repository that the content is being ingested to Europeana.

The LoCloud repository is built using the software MORE and has been developed into a cloud-based system in LoCloud following experience gained in several Europeana projects. The majority of LoCloud content will be ingested into Europeana via MORE.

In addition to being a repository management application, MORE also exposes a variety of useful API functions for data-access. It includes harvesting interfaces that permit Europeana to ingest content from it, methods that permit read/write access to metadata sources stored in the repository, and methods that user is able to transform the dataset from an intermediate schema to the target (EDM). Last but not least, MORE is one of the key integration points for the LoCloud micro services and the content-flow from provider to Europeana.

During the training partners were introduced to the features of MORE, and then they could try to harvest their own data (e.g. published via LoCloud Collections in previous part of the training) and configure the processing of that data, according to the ingestion workflow of MORE.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/MORE>

Deliverable: D2.3. Modified MORE (LoCloud) Aggregator Prototype

2.5 MINT

While the task of extracting metadata from local collection management systems is left to the individual system, the process of transforming and loading it into the LoCloud repository is greatly facilitated by the MINT tool. Here, data from different source metadata profiles can be brought in and mapped to a target model, i.e. the EDM data model, suitable for ingestion into Europeana.

MINT is a tool that supports content providers' metadata mapping and ingestion process. MINT is two things: an end-user application with a graphical user interface that simplifies complex cross-mapping tasks between different metadata schemas. MINT also exposes an API that permits a remote client to execute data and mapping functions via REST Web Services.

During the training partners were introduced to the features of MINT and then they were asked to register in the service, harvest or upload example dataset (or their own data), define mapping to EDM and process the data. Integration between MINT and MORE was also explained.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/MINT>

Deliverable: D2.2. Modified MINT prototype

2.6 Geolocation Enrichment Tools

With the wide range of topics, languages and institutions that are brought together through Europeana, geography is a promising means of creating integrated views of Europeana information. However, while there are ample geographical references, i.e. geographical names, in cultural heritage data, there is a limited amount of spatial coordinates available in the metadata. Spatial coordinates are required in order to be able to integrate data from different countries, independent of languages, terminology or thematic domains.

For the above reason, LoCloud has implemented a set of geolocation enrichment tools that consist of two parts. The first is a geolocation API (LoGeo) that provides geographical names search capabilities towards a variety of internal and external sources via a REST API; the second a geocoding, application that permits end-users to add high-resolution geolocations to non-spatial metadata records in a web based crowd-sourcing environment.

The training workshops emphasized the geocoding application as it has a user interface that allows institutions to work with their own data and add spatial coordinates either through plotting them in a map - or through linking them to entries in databases of well-known geographical names locations.

After an introduction, the workshop attendants tried to prepare, upload, geocode and download a sample dataset. Following the workshops, it is the intention that participants will be able to use the application with their own data – and demonstrate it to interested third parties.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/Geolocation%20Enrichment%20Tools>

Deliverable: D3.2. Geolocation enrichment tools

2.7 Historical Place Names Service

Many collection management systems deal with names simply as text-strings, not identifying absolutely which geographical entity a name represents, i.e. if an object is linked to the “Blue Mountains”, the systems relies on the contextual knowledge of the user in order to determine which Blue Mountains (out of many). Another issue is that the geographical area represented by a name changes over time – and that the names of areas changes over time. In order to address this problem it is necessary with a system like the LoCloud historical place name service that enables management of place names in both space and time. The resulting geographical names source is usable both within local collection management systems – and as a matching source for auto-enrichment of content in the LoCloud repository.

The Historical Place Names service (HPN) is a complete system for collecting and managing historic place names that are widely referenced in cultural heritage sources. The HPN also includes an API for looking up names and locations based on historical geographical references.

The training workshop focused on presenting the idea behind the service and then introducing practical scenarios for using the service from the point of view of a regular user (searching for place name) and a service administrator (managing service, enriching service database).

Documentation URL:

<http://support.locloud.eu/LoCloud%20Historical%20Placenames%20Microservice>

Deliverable: D3.5. Historic place names service

2.8 Vocabulary Service

In the same way as spatial coordinates provides a mechanism for correlating content in Europeana based on location, the vocabulary service serves the same function in “semantic space”. By providing a structure where terms and concepts are defined and interrelated, the service constitutes a base line for linking of heritage resources across domains, institutions and languages.

The LoCloud vocabulary service is a customization of the software TremaTres, an open source vocabulary server and web application that handles both vocabularies, thesauri, taxonomies and other formal representation of knowledge classification systems.

The vocabulary services expose an API that can be used for the integration of the vocabularies into remote third party systems. Similarly, the API permits the integration of remotely stored concepts into the vocabulary tool. The web service API has been extended for the purpose of LoCloud in order to support multilingual vocabularies better.

The training workshop introduced the tool as well as how it may be used to build and maintain a vocabulary.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/LoCloud%20Vocabulary%20Microservice>

Deliverable: D3.4. Vocabulary services

2.9 Enrichment Service

The content that is harvested from local collection management systems was often entered into the system with a very different purpose than presenting it to external end-users. Often it is merely a cataloguing system internal to the institution - and if any extended metadata are available, interpreting them can be difficult. Providing a richer context for the interpretation and understanding of digital cultural heritage objects is important. For this reason, LoCloud implements services for auto-enrichment of existing heritage resources. These are implemented as Web Services that are invoked within the MORE repository and do not have a separate graphical end-user interface.

The enrichment service is a Web Service API that does two things:

- Processes input records (in standard metadata formats) and outputs links to relevant background resources from Wikipedia. This API may be implemented by applications that loop through metadata records for existing collections in order to look up additional contextual resources.
- Processes input records and matches them to entries in a controlled vocabulary – making it possible to link heterogeneous content to a common semantic structure that will facilitate exploratory browsing.

There is no end-user interface for these two enrichment services. They are implemented as REST Web Services. At the training workshops, the service was demonstrated as part of the enrichment features that are invoked from the MORE repository.

The technical documentation is suitable for parties who would like to implement the services in their own applications.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/LoCloud%20Enrichment%20Microservice>

Deliverable: D3.3. Metadata Enrichment Services

2.10 Support Mechanism

The LoCloud support portal is a dedicated web site that is the focal point for all publicly accessible technical information about LoCloud services and applications.

The target audience for the support portal is LoCloud partners but all information will be made publicly available both throughout the project execution period and beyond for the benefit of third parties who would like to utilize LoCloud services and applications to provide additional functionality for their own applications and systems.

The LoCloud partnership consists of a broad range of different organization whereof some have a strictly technical focus whereas others are heritage professionals. The purpose of the support portal is to give easy access to all documentation and knowhow about the LoCloud outputs to facilitate the adoption of services and applications by both groups; i.e. both (1) the heritage professionals who have varying skills with regard to information technology as well as (2) the programmers who implement the various public APIs.

The training workshop provided attendants with information on how to access and use the support mechanism including what type of information is available, how to raise support tickets and how to use the interactive questions-and-answers system.

Documentation URL: <http://support.locloud.eu/>

Deliverable: D4.1. Documentation and help desk, D4.2. Live support portal

3 Video Recordings of Training Sessions

During the training workshop in Poznań, all presenters were asked to deliver their tutorials twice: once for the attendees of the workshop, and a second time in PSNC television studio, to be recorded for the purpose of creating of on-line video training materials. After the recording all the materials will be post-processed and published on-line during spring-early summer 2015 (D4.4).

Figure 4: Recording of MINT training session – TV studio view (21.11.2014)

Figure 5: Recording of MINT training session – control room view (21.11.2014)

Figure 6: Recording of MINT training session – HD video preview

4 Conclusions

During the training workshops the LoCloud tools such as LoCloud Collections, MINT, MORE and the microservices were presented. Partners discussed how to make the tools available to their local partner institutions during and after the project as well as functional and technical issues related to the software. Various issues were addressed. Some of the topics discussed were of general interest for all services; others were specific issues connected to each tool or service. Below selected issues that appeared or were discussed during the workshops are presented.

4.1 Improvement of Workshop Organisation

Agenda proposed for the first training workshop had the following layout of four content blocks:

- Day 1
 - LoCloud Collections
 - Microservices
- Day 2
 - MINT
 - MORE

During the first training, it came out that MINT and MORE sessions were too short (so they were prolonged). For the second and third training, the order of content blocks was the following:

- Day 1
 - LoCloud Collections
 - MORE
- Day 2
 - MINT
 - Microservices

The benefits of that change were the following:

- Having MINT and MORE in separate days allowed to make these sessions longer than initially, as the second day was shorter than the first one (to allow participants fly back on the same day). During the second and third workshop, it was clearly visible that the timing of sessions was good, allowing participants to get familiar with tools and try them on their own.
- Having MORE directly after LoCloud Collections allowed participants to start the training by going through entire basic workflow – from building their own digital library, to aggregating it in MORE, to processing and making ready for harvesting by Europeana.
- The second day was devoted to more advanced topics like complex metadata mapping in MINT. Also having microservices at the end allowed participants to understand better what the benefits of using these services are, as they had in mind recent experiences with LoCloud Collections, MORE and MINT. For example, they could compare the possibilities of basic geolocation of content available in LoCloud Collections with advanced possibilities of Geolocation Enrichment Tools.

4.2 Input to the improvement cycle of individual services

4.2.1 Multilingualism of end-user interfaces

Translation of user interface into national language is crucial for users from small institutions. It is to be discussed further how to deal with translations of services and tools. It should be determined which tools will be used by small institutions directly (see section about target groups below) and how to handle translations of these tools interfaces. The crucial aspect here is that software evolves and translations must follow changes made in the base language version of the interface.

Each partner taking responsibility for translation to his or her language could be a solution. Organizing of some sort of national crowdsourcing for translation among specific stakeholders is also a possible way to go for solving this issue.

4.2.2 Target group for each service

The descriptions/documentation provided for each tool and services needs to address target groups and user scenarios. Adding different user stories and descriptions of situations where tools could be used and describing how they fit into various workflows could be helpful. This could help small institutions to choose the most advantageous tools for their specific needs.

In addition to videos recorded in Poznań (which show a step-by-step demonstration of each tool or service) show cases and user stories will be added to documentation.

4.2.3 More simple user interfaces

Feedback from all three workshops showed that user interfaces of the tools and services that will be used directly by small institutions could be simplified further. There is a need to go through terms used in these interfaces and to work on the design of some elements to improve the user experience. The overall conclusion is nevertheless that user interfaces for the tools and services presented during workshop are quite good, but need some improvement that easily could be done with small changes.

4.2.4 Plugins to hide some parts of the workflow

For further improvement of the content provider workflow, the possibility of using plugins to integrate/hide some of the tools was discussed. This could help to make the user experiences better, especially for smaller and less experienced institutions. If some steps in the workflow could be hidden, the tools would be easier to use. The integration of tools could also be seamless.

4.3 Relations between LoCloud services

The cloud-based technology infrastructure enables the aggregation of local content and the micro-services help to reduce technical, semantic and skills barriers for content providing institutions and help to render their content so that it is more discoverable and interoperable. However, the relation between the different services not yet clear or easily understandable enough for content providing institutions.

The need for a guide to explain to small institutions how different tools and services are related and how they may be useful together was addressed in the workshops. LoCloud Support Centre introduces the applications, APIs and microservices including service descriptions, technical documentation, end-user manuals, frequently asked questions (FAQs) and demo installations where the services can be tested in a "sandbox" environment. It was suggested that a demonstration of how the different tools are related should be created and published there. The demo could be shown as a

guided product tour presenting how an unpublished collection with little metadata in a small institution can end up as enriched and discoverable content in Europeana.

A main issue in all workshops was the number of logins (passwords and usernames) necessary for accessing different LoCloud tools and services. There are five services and two support tools in LoCloud that authenticate users. It would be preferable to have a single username and password for all services across LoCloud to make access simpler. There should be also no limit of the number of accounts per partner institution.

Base addresses (URLs) of services could also be more standardised (e.g. all under locloud.eu domain).

4.4 Next steps

Partners involved in WP4 will continue to develop training materials available online via LoCloud Support Centre (<http://support.locloud.eu>). As a part of this work package, two new types of training resources will be provided:

- Presentations from training workshops and documentation available in Support Centre will be used to create e-learning courses which will be made available as part of the support centre (<http://support.locloud.eu/courses/>).
- Videos of training sessions recorded in Poznań will be processed and published on line in the Support Centre portal as a multimedia extension of existing documentation.

On the other hand, all LoCloud partners were encouraged during the workshop to reuse gained knowledge to promote LoCloud services in their countries and support the adoption of these services. To secure that LoCloud partners are able to utilize training materials used in workshops to organize local workshops (some partners like CG33 already did that). Partners can also translate the selected content of the documentation available in the support portal into their languages. Example of such translation can be seen in the documentation of LoCloud Collections (to switch between language versions users should click globe icon visible in the top right corner of the website):

- English version: <http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=LoCloud+Collections%3A+Basic+User+Guide>
- Polish version: http://support.locloud.eu/tiki-index.php?page=LoCloud%20Collections:%20Podstawowy%20podr%C4%99cznik%20u%C5%BCytkownika&no_bl=y

When e-learning courses will be made available, LoCloud partners can consider translations of these courses as well.

5 Appendices

5.1 Appendix I: Workshop Programme

The programme presented below was used during workshops in Poznań and Graz. The programme for first workshop in Bordeaux had slightly different ordering and timing of few tutorials, but it was adapted during the training to match the needs of participants. This resulted in changes of the official programme of second and third workshop. Section 4 of this deliverable provides more details about that.

Slides used during the training are available on the project website:

<http://www.locloud.eu/Events/LoCloud-Training-Workshops/Workshop-presentations>

5.1.1 Day 1

From	To	Topic - training track	Speakers (main speakers are underlined)
09:00	09:20	Welcome, introduction to the workshop	<u>Marcin Werla</u> (PSNC)
09:20	10:45	LoCloud Collections – presentation	
10:45	11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11:00	12:00	LoCloud Collections – exercises	<u>Marcin Werla</u> (PSNC)
12:00	12:15	Feedback/Discussion	
12:15	13:15	<i>Lunch</i>	
13:15	14:30	MORE - presentation	<u>Dimitris Gavrilis</u> , <u>Eleni Afiontzi</u> (ATHENA)
14:30	14:45	<i>Coffee break</i>	
14:45	15:45	MORE - exercises	<u>Stavros Angelis</u> , <u>Dimitra-Nefeli Makri</u> (ATHENA)
15:45	16:00	Feedback/Discussion	<u>Dimitris Gavrilis</u> , <u>Dimitra-Nefeli Makri</u> (ATHENA)
16:00	16:30	LoCloud Support Center	<u>Runar Bergheim</u> , <u>Siri Slettvåg</u> (AVINET)
16:30	16:45	Summary	<u>Marcin Werla</u> (PSNC)

5.1.2 Day 2

From	To	Topic	Speakers (main speakers are underlined)
09:00	10:00	MINT - presentation	<u>Vassilis Tzouvaras</u> , <u>Nasos Drosopoulos</u> , <u>Eleni Iskou</u> (NTUA)
10:00	11:00	MINT - exercises	
11:00	11:15	Feedback/Discussion	
11:15	11:30	<i>Coffee break</i>	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:30	12:30	Geolocation Enrichment Service	<u>Runar Bergheim</u> , <u>Siri Slettvåg</u> (AVINET)
12:30	13:00	Historic Place Names Service	<u>Rimvydas Laužikas</u> , <u>Ingrida Vosyliūtė</u> (VUKF)
13:00	14:00	<i>Lunch</i>	
14:00	14:45	Vocabulary Services	<u>Walter Koch</u> , <u>Gerda Koch</u> (AIT)

From	To	Topic	Speakers (main speakers are underlined)
14:45	15:00	Summary, closing	<u>Runar Bergheim</u> , <u>Siri Slettvåg</u> (AVINET)

5.1.3 Main Speakers Biographies

Speakers are listed in alphabetical order of their surnames.

- **Stavros Angelis** is a Scientific Associate at DCU. His research interests include digital preservation, digital libraries, metadata and he has been involved in the design and development of MOPSEUS and the CARARE repository and in the DARIAH, CARARE and EHRI.
- **Runar Bergheim** is an all-rounder within information technology and geo-information, has 14 years of experience from European projects and is currently taking part in several Europeana-related activities. Being at the helm of technical work packages in the EuropeanaLocal project.
- **Dimitris Gavrilis** is a Scientific Associate at DCU. His research interests include digital library architectures, interoperability between digital library systems and he has been involved in the design and development of MOPSEUS and the CARARE repository and in the DARIAH, CARARE and EHRI.
- **Walter Koch** is director of AIT Ltd. and professor at the University of Graz (lecturer in the European Masters programme for "European Heritage, Digital Media and the Information Society). Member of several national and international scientific associations (e.g. Board member of CIDOC/ICOM) / 40 years' experience in international research projects: bibliographic information, information systems, IT- management (ESA, UNESCO, EU etc.)
- **Rimvydas Laužikas** has been an Assistant Professor for VUKF since 2005. In 1998 – 2008 he was Chief Curator of Collections and Archaeologist for the Lithuanian Museum of Ethno cosmology. R. Laužikas is also a representative of Lithuania for ISO/TC 211 Geographic information/Geomatics. His research interests include the Archaeology of churches in Lithuania, digitisation of the cultural heritage, digital technologies for scientific research and museology.
- **Siri Slettvåg** has more than 20 years experiences from decision making, planning, strategy and project management in the GLAM sector in Norway. She has been involved in initiatives for open access, open culture on national and international level, development of a various digital services and outreach programs in the museum and archive sector. The last ten years she has been a key person regarded to copyright questions and licensing and for promoting use of new technologies and user involvement.
- **Vassilis Tzouvaras** has a B-Eng in the Dept. of Electronic & Systems Engineering of Essex University, M-Eng in the Dept. of Automatic Control & Systems Engineering of Sheffield University in UK, and the Ph.D. in the EECE Dept. of NTUA in the field of knowledge technologies. He is active in the Europeana developments and many related projects (Athena, Videoactive, Euscreen).
- **Marcin Werla**, has led the PSNC Digital Libraries Team since 2004. His professional interests include architecture of digital libraries, the integration of resources of distributed digital libraries and software engineering, especially software products management. He is strongly involved in many Europeana activities related to Polish cultural and scientific institutions, including projects such as Europeana Local and Europeana Awareness.

5.2 Appendix II: Attendance Lists

Copy of signed attendance sheets

5.2.1 Bordeaux, France, 23-24.10.2014

LoCloud Training Workshop

Date: 23 + 24 OCTOBER 2014

Place: BORDEAUX, GIRONDE, FRANCE.

Participants list

Name and surname	Affiliation	Signature
SILVIA ALFREIDER	NRA	Silvia Alfreider
MARTIN KRASNJAK	PIFUK KREG	Martin Krasnjak
Tatiana Shamalina-Keidenredt	UDE	Tatiana Shamalina-Keidenredt
SARA VUKUSIC	GKR	Sara Vukusic
RENE BEKUS	GKR	Rene Bekus
Paical GESESTE	ADGironde	Paical Geseste
Bart Boer	RCE	Bart Boer
Dimitris Gavrilis	Athens R.C	Dimitris Gavrilis
Agnes Stefinsdottir	ATHI	Agnes Stefinsdottir
Konstantinos Kravvaritis	Athens RC	Konstantinos Kravvaritis
ΖΑΖΑΝΑ ΠΡΟΣΒΑ	NPÜ	Zazana Prosva
IKENA ALTIKOVA	-11-	Ikena Altikova
ELENI ISKOV	NTUA	Eleni Iskov
Vassilis Tzouvaras	NTUA	Vassilis Tzouvaras
KATE FERNIE	ZCULTURE	Kate Fernie
MARCIN WERLA	PSNC	Marcin Werla

5.2.2 Poznań, Poland, 20-21.11.2014

LoCloud Training Workshop

Date: 20/21.11.2014

Place: POZNAŃ, POLAND

Participants list

Name and surname	Affiliation	Signature
FRANC ZAKRASEK	IPCHS	
RIMYDAS LAUSKAS	VUKF	
KOCH WALTER	AIT- GRAZ	
LOUISE KENNEDY	DISCOVERY PROGRAMME	
KATE FENNE	ZCULTURE	
NKOS DROSPOULOS	NTUA	
ERTÉ Eleni Istou	NTUA	
GYORFFY ANDRÁS-TIBOR	COUZY, LIDRÁRYCZY	
STEIN RUNAR-BERGHEIM	AVINET	
SIRI SLETTVÅG	AVINET	
GUNNAR URTEGAARD	NATIONAL ARCHIVES	
Holly Wright	VOY-ADS	
Beynė Hrozi	PCSS	
JEFF MALLIET	Pres. Limburg(B)	
MARIA CARRILLO CARE TUNDIÖR	MECD - STATE MUSEUM	
DOMINGO ARROYO	MECD	
BLAZI J BĚTANSKI	PCS -	
Marion Wake	PCSS	

5.2.3 Graz, Austria, 11-12.12.2014

LoCloud Training
Workshop

Date: 11.12.2014 - 12.12.2014

Place: Graz, Austria

Participants list

Name and surname	Affiliation	Signature
GERDA KOCH	AIT	
ELENI ISKOU	NTUA	
NIKOS SIMOU	NTUA	
SIRI SLETTVÅG	AVINET	
GUUNAR VIKTESSAND	National Archive Norway	
DIMITRA-NEFELI MARI	DCU (ATHENA RC)	
Afionzi Eleni	DCU (ATHENA RC)	
KRISTINE HOFF MEYER	KUAS AGENCY FOR CULTURE	
PREDRAG ĐUKIĆ	BELGRADE CITY LIBRARY	
Jasmina Ninkov	Belgrade City Library	
Vangelis Banos	Future Library	
BREDA KARUN	Zavod Jaru	
Zaska Kalcheva	Public Library Varna	
Duygu Ölgür	VEKAM Library	
Abu Ayoskur	VEKAM Library	
Tolpa GAKMAK	Hacettepe University	

Name and surname	Affiliation	Signature
DIDO BENDA	AIT	
WALTER KOCH	AIT	
KATE FERNIE	ZCULTURE	
COSTIS DALLAS	DCU/ARC	
MARCIN WERLA	PSNC	